

Event metadata

Event title	WORKSHOP: RNAseq: reads to differential expression
Event type	Workshop
Date of event	10 - 11 September 2024
Time of event	1:00 - 4:30 pm AEST
Topic description	<p>RNA-Seq is a popular method for measuring differential gene expression. This hands-on workshop introduces the concepts of RNA-Seq analysis, from data preparation through to statistical testing for differential gene expression. You'll learn how to use popular tools and workflows to analyse the data, produce graphical summaries and identify differentially expressed genes.</p> <p>The workshop will focus on the use of Galaxy, a web-based platform for accessible, reproducible, and transparent computational biological research. Widely used by researchers world wide, Galaxy gives you access to 1000's of popular tools for analysis and processing of biological data. Galaxy Australia is a fully subsidised service provided by Australian BioCommons.</p>
Format description	<p>Workshop, online via Zoom over two three and a half hour sessions.</p> <p>Mike Thang led the training by introducing key concepts and demonstrating the steps involved in the analysis. Participants then completed code along exercises giving them a chance to apply these skills with support from facilitators.</p> <p>In parallel to the live session, Zoom Chat was used to answer questions as they arose, troubleshoot and share tips and resources.</p> <p>The workshop followed the Galaxy Training Network Tutorials:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RNAseq: reads to counts • RNAseq counts to genes <p>A breakdown of timings and topics is provided in the schedule (provided in this Zenodo record).</p> <p>Participation was free but subject to application with selection.</p> <p>Applications were reviewed by the organising committee.</p> <p>Number of participants = 34</p>

Identifier(s)/URL	https://www.biocommons.org.au/events/rnaseq-2024
Licence	Materials are shared under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International agreement unless otherwise stated on the materials
Keywords	Bioinformatics http://edamontology.org/topic_0091 Analysis http://edamontology.org/operation_2945 RNA-seq http://edamontology.org/topic_3170 Transcriptomics http://edamontology.org/topic_3308
Contact	training@biocommons.org.au
Audience	Australian researchers and life scientists who will use RNA-seq for differential gene expression as part of their projects.
Prerequisites	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> You must be associated with an Australian organisation for your application to be considered Some familiarity with Galaxy is encouraged. We recommend watching this brief introduction to Galaxy Australia and working through the Galaxy Basics for Everyone tutorial before joining the workshop.
Technical requirements	<p>Online Platform</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Zoom <p>Participants required:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Laptop with access to the internet, speakers, a webcam, microphone and Zoom. <p>Training infrastructure</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The workshop made use of Galaxy Australia's Training Infrastructure as a Service (TlaaS)
Learning outcomes	<p>By the end of the workshop you should be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Perform QC evaluation and filtering on next-generation sequencing data Use tools in Galaxy to identify differentially expressed genes from RNA-Seq data
Lead Trainers	Mike Thang, Galaxy Australia / QCIF
Facilitators	Dr Selene Fernandez Valverde
Related work	<p>This tutorial is part of the Galaxy Training Network:</p> <p>https://training.galaxyproject.org/training-material/</p>